

AI REGIO project: AI4Manufacturing Toolkit taxonomies

AI REGIO project (“Regions and DIHs alliance for AI-driven digital transformation of European Manufacturing SMEs”, GA 952003) is building a one-stop-shop platform that enables access to resources for AI-based solutions in efficient and sustainable manufacturing, with particular emphasis on resources that can lower the AI adoption barriers for SMEs. At technological level several platforms are going to be developed, including the one known as **AI4Manufacturing Toolkit**.

AI4Manufacturing Toolkit is "a collection of operational technologies, data analytics tools and platforms, designed to provide support to system integrators and technology adopters to create new AI-based applications". There are three taxonomies in the catalogue, which aim to facilitate end-user reuse and adoption of existing resources:

1. AI Asset Type: Main taxonomy for the AI4Manufacturing toolkit. There are 3 main type of entities:

AI Asset Type	
AI resource	Reusable machine learning or deep learning models to solve a specific manufacturing problem
AI pipeline designer	Where a set of AI resources are composed in a workflow
AI orchestrator	End-to-end application where several AI pipelines or AI resources are managed/orchestrated

2. Artificial Intelligence Categories: Additional taxonomy for semantic enrichment focus on AI domain. In line with AI Technical Categories defined by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in the second version of its report “[AI Watch - Defining Artificial Intelligence](#)”. This categorization is also used by the [AI4EU platform](#).

Artificial Intelligence Categories	
Reasoning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge representation • Automated reasoning • Common sense reasoning
Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning and scheduling • Searching • Optimisation
Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Machine learning
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural language processing
Perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computer vision • Audio processing
Integration and Interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-agent systems • Robotics and Automation • Connected and Automated vehicles
Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI services
Ethics and Philosophy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI ethics • Philosophy of AI

3. AI REGIO Manufacturing Categories: Additional taxonomy for semantic enrichment focus on manufacturing domain. Defined ad-hoc for our project, mixing some of the other proposals (coming both from internal and external contributions). This is a dynamic categorization, open to changes and modifications, which will be expanded/improved as the project progresses.

AI REGIO Manufacturing Categories	
Product development/R&D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New product development • Product validation in R&D • Product enhancement
Demand Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demand planning/forecasting • Digital Twins
Inventory Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Order optimization • Inventory planning
Process Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real time-optimization of process parameters • Optimize equipment changeover • Digital Twins
Production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimizing overall productivity in the product line • Computer vision for product identification • Layout planning • Collaborative robots (cobots)/ Human Robot Collaboration • Flexible Manufacturing • Sustainable Manufacturing • Human Centred Manufacturing • Digital Twins • Zero Defect Manufacturing • Zero waste
Quality Control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product quality inspection • Predicting final product quality • Quality Management
Supply Chain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply Chain Management • Circular Chain Management
Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intelligent maintenance/ Predictive maintenance • Energy management • Worker safety • Scrap/wastage reduction • Increasing equipment efficiency • Asset Management • Digital Twins

In this **AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories_v2.7z** file all these previous categories have been defined as taxonomies (using different formats), and made available to the general public for re-use.

File Name	Format file					Language	
	RDF (SKOS)	XLSX	CSV	TXT	XML	English	Spanish
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-EN_v2.csv			X			X	
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-EN_v2.txt				X		X	
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-EN_v2.xml					X	X	
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-EN+ES_v2.rdf	X					X	X
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-EN+ES_v2.xlsx		X				X	X
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-ES_v2.csv			X				X
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-ES_v2.txt				X			X
AI REGIO-AI4ManufacturingToolkitCategories-ES_v2.xml					X		X